

Arctic as a point of convergence between Russian and Chinese interests: Emerging trends and constraints in 2025

Sergei Gladkov

Pan-European Institute, Department of Marketing and International Business, Turku School of Economics, University of Turku, Finland

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Abstract

This article examines the emerging trends in Russia's and China's approaches to Arctic development and the degree of institutionalization of their bilateral cooperation in 2025. The analysis demonstrates that the two sides are converging tactically, yet remain strategically divergent. For Russia, the Arctic is framed as a long-term pillar of national development and international positioning, consolidated through the concept of the Trans-Arctic Transport Corridor (TATC) and reinforced by legal and organizational measures. China, in contrast, seeks to integrate the Arctic into the broader framework of "global autonomization" and the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), linking it to the development of the Russian Far East and positioning its engagement as a response to Russia's sanctions-induced isolation in the context of the war in Ukraine. Russia has been actively strengthening the institutional foundations of its Arctic strategy, whereas China is in the process of refining its approaches, drawing on its 2018 Arctic Policy White Paper and adapting them to unfolding geopolitical shifts. These processes remain precariously balanced, and the resilience of Sino-Russian cooperation in the Arctic depends on external dynamics as well as the capacity of both sides to reconcile their priorities.

Keywords

Russia; China; Arctic region; strategic approaches; institutionalization of cooperation; Northern Sea Route

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1. Introduction

The rapid evolution of the geopolitical environment in 2025 has had a significant impact on the Arctic. The growing interest in the region—military, economic, and environmental—has intensified under the influence of external factors and the involvement not only of the Arctic states but also of other powers seeking to secure benefits and expand their spheres of influence, with China representing the most prominent case. At this stage, China has sought to counter U.S. tariff measures; however, the escalation of this confrontation has compelled Beijing to adopt preventive measures aimed at securing stable energy supplies and diversifying external trade routes. A particular focus is placed on the strategic vulnerability of the Malacca Strait, which China perceives as subject to U.S. control. The urgency of such measures is further reinforced by mounting economic challenges coupled with a deteriorating demographic situation (García-Herrero, 2025; Reuters, 2025a). In light of these dynamics, China views partnership with Russia in the Arctic—enabling the creation of an alternative transport corridor—as both a viable option and a key element of its strategy to enhance the autonomy of external economic relations, notwithstanding significant geopolitical risks and technical constraints.

Against this background, China is gradually developing theoretical foundations for refining its Arctic policy, originally articulated in the White Paper (China’s State Council, 2018), and adapting it to the rapidly changing geopolitical environment. Although these new approaches have not yet been formally institutionalized, they are increasingly visible in theoretical studies (Li et al., 2025; Zhang, 2025; Guo and Li, 2025) and related research. A common feature of these approaches is a comprehensive vision of Arctic engagement—integrating transport, energy, science, and culture—while further embedding the region into the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). Within this framework, Russia is assigned a special role as a pivotal partner in the development of routes and infrastructure.

In parallel, Russia in 2025 has markedly intensified the institutionalization of its Arctic policy by adopting a series of strategic documents¹ and launching the implementation of the TATC—a broader conceptualization of the Northern Sea Route (NSR). At this year’s St. Petersburg International Economic Forum (SPIEF), the Arctic emerged as one of the central topics. Russia’s strategy places particular emphasis on safeguarding its interests in the Arctic through the modernization of its naval capabilities and the infrastructural development of Arctic territories, while also envisaging expanded practical cooperation with China, especially in logistics and energy.

While Russia and China demonstrate overlapping interests in harnessing Arctic opportunities and have expanded practical cooperation, their broader strategic approaches remain divergent. Existing contradictions are not being resolved but are instead relegated to the periphery of interaction under the pressure of current circumstances, with no clear indication of whether these tensions will escalate or diminish.

China views its Arctic cooperation with Russia in close connection with the development of engagement in the Russian Far East. From Beijing’s strategic perspective, this region

¹ See, for example: Presidential Directive No. Pr-1079 of 16 May 2025 (Prikaz Prezidenta Rossiyskoy Federatsii, 2025); Russia’s Energy Strategy to 2050 (April 2025) (Russian Government, 2025a); Implementation Plan for the Spatial Development Strategy of the Russian Federation to 2030 (August 2025) (Russian Government, 2025b)

constitutes a key element of an expanded Eurasian architecture, into which transport, energy, cultural, and humanitarian cooperation are organically interwoven. Russia, for its part, seeks to strengthen ties through its Far Eastern territories not only with China but also with other Asian states and the broader Asia-Pacific region.

This article focuses on Sino-Russian cooperation in the Arctic in 2025, examining the emerging trends in how both countries perceive and strategically approach Arctic development. Its aim is to identify the specific features of these approaches and to analyze the degree of institutionalization of bilateral interaction. To achieve this, the study sets the following tasks: (1) to trace the transformation of Chinese and Russian strategic orientations in the Arctic; (2) to assess the institutional mechanisms of bilateral cooperation; and (3) to identify contradictions as well as potential areas of convergence.

The methodological foundation of the study includes an analysis of official documents of Russia and China, the proceedings of international forums, expert commentaries, and publications in specialized media. Particular attention is given to current publications that capture the rapidly evolving changes in the positions of both sides. These materials are essential for analyzing Russian and Chinese statements and approaches that have not yet been reflected in official strategic documents or academic research. At the same time, the limitations of news sources are taken into account: their high dynamism and susceptibility to short-term fluctuations require critical interpretation and comparison with more stable strategic orientations.

2. Contemporary approaches of China and Russia to the Arctic in 2025

In 2025, the Arctic is increasingly consolidating its position as one of the key arenas of international politics and the global economy. Climate change is expanding opportunities for resource development and the use of Arctic transport routes, while intensifying geopolitical competition adds further strategic weight to the region. For Russia, the Arctic is perceived as part of its national territory, integrated into the objectives of socio-economic development and the strengthening of sovereignty. By contrast, China regards the Arctic as an external regional framework that supports the diversification of logistical and energy channels under conditions of global instability. These fundamentally different starting positions predetermine the divergence in how the two sides shape their Arctic policies.

Amid the escalating U.S.–China confrontation, strained relations with the EU, and the stagnation of traditional structures of international Arctic cooperation—above all the Arctic Council—Russia remains for Beijing virtually the only gateway to the Arctic. While this dimension is rarely highlighted in Chinese discourse, cooperation with Russia enables China to participate in regional projects and strengthen its polar expertise (Leksyutina, 2025). Over time, collaboration with Russia in this sphere has allowed China to develop its own Arctic competencies and plan for the use of Arctic routes to diversify trade and economic ties. This has given Beijing—despite its non-Arctic status—the ability to regard the region as a strategic resource base and transit platform. Nevertheless, the subsequent evolution of the international environment has significantly altered the framework conditions for China's Arctic policy.

Following the outbreak of the war in Ukraine in 2022, the sanctions imposed on Russia, and the subsequent deterioration of the international environment, the Arctic has come to represent for China less a "zone of cooperation" than a domain of heightened risk and uncertainty. The Chinese perspective frames this situation as a threefold challenge: the intensification of great-power military activity, the erosion of established multilateral formats, and the growing barriers to economic initiatives (Zhao and Zhang, 2024). Under these conditions, China has taken steps to safeguard its "rights and interests" in the Arctic. One priority has been the creation of a national legal framework regulating the activities of Chinese companies, setting environmental standards, and providing a juridical basis for a long-term Arctic presence. Another has been the pursuit of technological self-reliance: polar equipment, vessels, and research complexes are expected to reduce dependence on foreign partners and strengthen China's position in shipping and resource projects. These efforts are complemented by participation in the development of new mechanisms of Arctic governance in cooperation with states that possess the necessary resources—with Russia being the most important partner. Particular emphasis has also been placed on "scientific diplomacy": involvement in expeditions, joint programs, and climate monitoring enables China to project the image of a responsible actor, while scientific initiatives serve as an instrument of soft power that allows it to bypass political barriers and reinforce its status as a "near-Arctic state."

The intensification of Russian–American negotiations in spring 2025, including on Arctic issues, has raised concerns in China regarding Moscow's future priorities: whether it will maintain its previous focus on cooperation with Beijing or redirect attention toward Washington. China's anxiety stems from the possibility of a shift in the balance of power in the Arctic. Should Russia reduce its dependence on China and involve the United States in joint projects in shipping, energy, and infrastructure, this could jeopardize the development of the "Polar Silk Road" and undermine Beijing's efforts to consolidate its position as a "near-Arctic state" (The Epoch Times, 2025b). This prospect heightens China's sense of vulnerability and

compels it to balance between sustaining cooperation with Moscow and preparing for potential U.S. pressure. For the moment, the balance remains tilted toward deepening cooperation with Russia in the Arctic, although Sino-Russian relations in this sphere are more transactional than strategic: Moscow maintains strict control over access to the region and permits Chinese participation only on specific, albeit advantageous, terms, typically as a minority partner. At the same time, continuing sanctions against Russia and the war in Ukraine are increasing Moscow's dependence on Beijing, thereby objectively expanding the scope for Chinese influence. In seeking long-term stability, China is turning to institutional and conceptual instruments designed to lend greater resilience to its Arctic policy.

In this situation, as it becomes necessary to account for emerging risks and uncertainties, China seeks institutional and conceptual anchors for its evolving Arctic course. The most notable of these is the linkage of the Arctic with the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and the formulation of the so-called "Global Arctic" concept.

The BRI, launched in 2013, was expanded in 2015 to combine the Silk Road Economic Belt (Belt and Road portal, 2023b) and the 21st Century Maritime Silk Road (Belt and Road portal, 2023a) within the framework document *Vision and Actions on Jointly Building the Silk Road Economic Belt and the 21st-Century Maritime Silk Road* (Government of China, 2015). In the same year, Beijing issued the *Vision for Maritime Cooperation under the Belt and Road Initiative* (China's State Council, 2017), which consolidated directions of maritime cooperation, including a prospective Arctic dimension. In 2018, China's Arctic Policy White Paper formalized the concept of the Polar Silk Road, based on the NSR, referred to as the "Arctic sea route," and incorporated into the BRI (China's State Council, 2018). Unlike Russia, China interprets the NSR as an international trade corridor intended for joint use.

Following the outbreak of the war in Ukraine, China began to reassess its Arctic policy, adapting it to the rapidly changing geopolitical environment and to Russia's "Turn to the East" (Zhang, 2025; Li et al., 2025). This process has not amounted to a wholesale overhaul but represents a discernible reframing in the theoretical literature, with formal institutionalization still pending. The common denominator in these approaches is a comprehensive program of Arctic engagement—integrating transport, energy, science, and culture—while deepening the region's incorporation into the BRI and the Polar Silk Road. In this vision, Russia's role is elevated: its confrontation with the West and sanctions-induced isolation, coupled with growing dependence on China, make Moscow an indispensable element of the emerging Arctic project. These conceptual developments are gradually beginning to be reflected in China's practical policies.

In practical terms, this implies the development of a multi-tier strategy encompassing transport, energy, the economy, science, and culture. On land, an important foundation is the linkage between China's Northeast and the Russian Far East, part of which falls within Russia's Arctic zone. The Chinese provinces of Heilongjiang, Jilin, and Liaoning—northeastern regions bordering Russia (Heilongjiang borders Amur Oblast, the Jewish Autonomous Region, and Primorsky Krai; Jilin borders Primorsky Krai; Liaoning borders the southern part of the Russian Far East)—constitute a strategic hinterland that strengthens logistical and economic connectivity with the Russian Arctic. At sea, the key hub is Dalian, a major port in Liaoning Province located about 250 km from the Russian border; at the turn of the twentieth century, it was leased by Russia as Dalniy (Port Arthur). Today it is positioned as the starting point of the Polar Silk Road—a route connecting China with Europe and the Americas. The next stage of cooperation is defined by the framework of the "Land-Ice Silk Road," which envisages the

integration of overland and maritime routes. Its central element is the Irtysh–Ob axis, providing access to the Arctic Ocean and linking China, Central Asia, and Russia. Transverse corridors are also envisioned toward Western and South Asia, as well as Africa. As a result, the Arctic becomes part of a global logistics architecture, with the Polar Silk Road functioning as the northern extension of the BRI.

Alongside material infrastructure, China attaches great importance to humanitarian and informational integration. It has proposed the creation of a Sino-Russian platform for cultural and informational exchange, encompassing international events, the popularization of Arctic knowledge, and the promotion of youth initiatives. Such a format could serve as an additional resource for consolidating China's institutional presence in the Arctic, particularly given its status as a near-Arctic state and its ambition to establish complementary governance platforms.

These initiatives fit organically into China's broader soft power strategy, which in the Arctic context is grounded in the concept of "交叉融合" (jiaocharonghe)—the cross-disciplinary integration of academia, policy, and practice. Research provides the analytical foundation for foreign policy, while international engagement is advanced through participation in Track II dialogues, conferences, and collaboration with global think tanks. Shanghai functions as a soft power hub, combining global events with academic output. The humanities and cultural initiatives feed into this model, and its flexibility allows soft power to be employed as an instrument of governance over global processes—ranging from the Arctic and cyberspace to BRICS and the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) (The Paper, 2025).

The second tier of soft power is manifested in the Arctic through semi-official publications, blogs, and specialized portals that disseminate narratives closely aligned with the state's position. They construct the image of China as a legitimate participant in Arctic affairs, emphasizing the peaceful nature of its expeditions and its technological capabilities. This dual framework—combining scientific openness with hard infrastructure—enables Beijing both to demonstrate the legitimacy of its presence and to reinforce its status as a technological power. Such texts often function as "trial balloons": the reaction of the international community determines whether these narratives remain unofficial or are subsequently absorbed into the official line (Tencent News, 2025).

Amid the ongoing war in Ukraine, intensifying sanctions pressure, and a slowdown in economic activity, Russia in 2025 is prioritizing the Arctic as a strategic project intended both to strengthen domestic economic security and to create opportunities for attracting foreign partners in order to mitigate the consequences of isolation from technologically advanced Western states.

An analysis of official statements made in the summer of 2025 indicates that the expansion of international cooperation in Arctic development has become a central priority. Russian diplomacy emphasizes openness to pragmatic engagement with all interested states, reaffirming the primacy of constructive cooperation (TASS, 2025d). At the same time, the need to form new partnerships with non-Arctic countries is underscored, with particular attention given to the development of transport and logistics routes, scientific exchanges, environmental initiatives, and tourism (Rossiyskaya Gazeta, 2025).

At the domestic political level, these priorities are reflected in the positions of the Federation Council. Senators stress the importance of maintaining at least a minimal level of dialogue among the Arctic states and highlight the prospects of cooperation with China, India, and

Southeast Asian countries, especially in the fields of logistics and energy, while at the same time regarding limited engagement with the United States, Canada, and Norway as important (Federation Council of Russia, 2025). At the regional level, the advisability of involving other states in Arctic development is emphasized, which, according to the State Commission on Arctic Development, could help accelerate the growth of the Russian sector of the region (TASS, 2025b).

Thus, the Russian approach is based not only on the aspiration to maintain its positions in the Arctic but also on the effort to build new channels of interaction, above all with the states of the Global South, for the joint development of Arctic territories and the utilization of their potential. Within this strategy, China occupies a special place, viewed as a key partner in the implementation of Arctic projects. The interest of other Asian countries is also assessed positively: the Russian Ministry of Foreign Affairs highlights the prospects for the return of South Korea—which possesses significant technological expertise considered essential for the development of the Russian Arctic—to the Russian market and to Arctic projects (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Russian Federation, 2025a). An additional example of expanding cooperation was provided by the negotiations between the foreign ministers of Russia and India, held in Moscow in August 2025: their outcome indicated that Moscow and New Delhi view joint projects on the extraction of resources on the Arctic shelf and in the Russian Far East as promising areas for cooperation (TASS, 2025g). It is expected that this topic will receive further development during the visit of Russian President Vladimir Putin to India, which may take place before the end of 2025.

In line with Russia's declared openness to international cooperation, the meeting between Putin and Trump in Alaska was regarded as an important test of the practical feasibility of this course. While in the official statements of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and the Federation Council the emphasis was placed on long-term readiness for cooperation and the preservation of dialogue even under conditions of confrontation, the expectations from negotiations with the United States were concentrated on specific areas of interaction. Forecasts of Russia's Presidential Administration Project Office for Arctic Development included ideas on joint solutions to environmental problems, the establishment of data management centers for the development of artificial intelligence technologies—including in the Arctic region (TASS, 2025e). The potential for collaboration in environmental protection, infrastructure, and energy was also underlined (RIA Novosti, 2025b, 2025c). According to sectoral experts, U.S. companies could become significant partners of Rosneft in the development of Arctic fields, which would simultaneously strengthen the positions of Russian energy corporations (Rosneft, Gazprom, Novatek) and enhance the investment attractiveness of the sector (Vedomosti, 2025c). According to Reuters, the U.S. administration even considered involving Russian nuclear icebreakers to support energy projects in Alaska, including natural gas and LNG production (Reuters, 2025b). However, the inflated expectations formed prior to the meeting quickly gave way to disappointment: positive forecasts on the financial markets were replaced by a decline in business confidence (RBC, 2025), which, according to Russian experts, was further linked to expectations of intensified sanctions pressure from the EU in the form of the 19th sanctions package (URA.RU, 2025).

An important factor remains that today the central backdrop for any discussion on the prospects of U.S.–Russian cooperation continues to be the negotiations on the possible end of the war in Ukraine, which have effectively relegated the Arctic agenda to the background. However, the logic of the declared priorities suggests that the conclusion of a peace treaty would inevitably

bring the Arctic back to the forefront as a strategic space in U.S.–Russian relations and as one of the key areas of potential economic cooperation.

Against this background, Russia seeks to use major events to consolidate its initiative on the Arctic agenda. This applies to the St. Petersburg International Economic Forum (SPIEF 2025) as well as to other international platforms hosted across the country during the summer of 2025. Among them were the "Arctic Salon" in St. Petersburg (August), the 17th International Conference on the Development of Arctic Oil and Gas Resources and the Continental Shelf of the CIS Countries (St. Petersburg, October), the 3rd Forum "Arctic — Regions 2025" in Arkhangelsk (July), the 4th All-Russian Youth Environmental Forum-Festival "Arctic. The Ice Has Broken" in Khanty-Mansiysk (July), and the 3rd Arctic Forum "The Future of Supply: Innovation, Technology, Leadership" in Yakutsk (June). Such a concentration of events underscores Moscow's intention to institutionalize the Arctic dimension, highlight its importance for national development, and attract international attention to Russian initiatives.

A larger-scale intensification of Russia's Arctic policy is planned for 2027. In the spring of 2025, an initiative was put forward to hold a "Year of the Arctic," initially scheduled for 2026. Its stated aim was to stimulate international participation and underscore the importance of Arctic territories for national development. This initiative was conceived both as a tool to strengthen Russia's position in Arctic affairs and as a mechanism to consolidate efforts to ensure the integrity and sustainable development of the Russian Arctic. However, it was later decided to synchronize the Year of the Arctic with the next international forum "Arctic — Territory of Dialogue." The forum, held in Murmansk with the participation of the President of Russia, demonstrated the potential of such a merger, becoming a prominent event that contributed to the activation of the Arctic agenda domestically. The postponement to 2027 is explained by the need to account for possible changes in the international environment (Vedomosti, 2025b). The underlying calculation is that by then the political and economic context may be more favorable, including prospects for a partial normalization of dialogue with the United States and other currently unfriendly states. Thus, the decision to shift the dates reflects Russia's broader strategy of sustaining its activity in Arctic affairs against the backdrop of growing international interest in the region.

In this context, Russian expert circles are actively discussing Arctic issues and the possible transformation of the national strategy in this sphere. In their assessments, the Arctic is viewed not only as a strategic source of raw materials but also as a space for international economic and scientific cooperation (RIA Novosti, 2025d). At the same time, the expert community (Russian Academy of Sciences; Vedomosti, 2025a) is considering the possibility of Russian gas returning to the European market, conditional on placing part of the key gas transportation infrastructure under U.S. control. Examples include initiatives by American investors regarding Nord Stream 2, the interest of private funds in Bulgaria's gas system, and discussions on incorporating Ukrainian infrastructure into a "resource deal" framework. It is also emphasized that the potential for U.S.–Russian cooperation in the Arctic is not confined to energy: promising areas are seen to include joint scientific research, expeditions, data exchange, cooperation in navigation and search-and-rescue operations, as well as high technologies (TASS, 2025a).

Overall, the assessments of Russian analytical institutions reveal a consistent effort to maintain balance: on the one hand, expanding ties with Asian partners such as China and India, and on the other, sustaining a minimal but necessary level of engagement with traditional Arctic states.

Despite the outward similarity of interests, the approaches of China and Russia to the Arctic in 2025 differ substantially. For Moscow, the Arctic constitutes an integral part of national territory and strategic development: it is integrated into the objectives of socio-economic growth, sovereignty strengthening, and institutional consolidation. For Beijing, by contrast, the Arctic represents an external regional framework used to diversify logistical and energy routes, reduce the vulnerability of external economic relations, and expand global presence.

China seeks to minimize geopolitical risks by embedding the Arctic dimension into the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and the "Global Arctic" concept, relying on instruments of soft power and network-based cooperation. Russia, by contrast, emphasizes strengthening domestic development, expanding institutional mechanisms, and seeking partners in the Global South, while maintaining at least a minimal level of dialogue with traditional Arctic states.

These differences do not preclude opportunities for cooperation: Sino-Russian partnership is developing in areas where their interests converge—notably in energy, logistics, and science. Yet the depth of cooperation is constrained by their divergent understandings of the Arctic: Russia views it as a national resource, whereas China interprets it as an international transit space. As a result, the character of interaction remains predominantly pragmatic and transactional, without a transition toward a full-fledged allied model.

For a clearer comparison of the main parameters of Russian and Chinese approaches, see Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of Russia’s and China’s basic approaches to the Arctic

Parameter	Russia	China
Basic perception	Integral part of national territory and long-term development strategy	External region, important for global diversification and resilience
Strategic objective	Strengthening sovereignty, socio-economic development, resource integration	Ensuring strategic autonomy, reducing vulnerability of supply chains
Resource factor	Exploitation and integration of Arctic resources into the national economy	Access to energy and raw materials as part of global diversification
Policy framework	Arctic Strategy 2035; Strategy for the Development of the Arctic Zone until 2035; Maritime Doctrine 2022	China’s Arctic Policy (2018 White Paper); Polar Silk Road within the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI)
Institutional focus	Centralized governance, federal coordination	External partnerships, selective institutional involvement
Time horizon	Long-term (to mid-21st century, 2050 planning horizon)	Medium-term, flexible and adaptive to global conditions
Geopolitical framing	Arctic as a sphere of sovereignty and internal consolidation	Arctic as an international logistics and energy corridor under multipolarity

Source: Compiled by the author based on official Russian and Chinese strategic documents, policy statements, and secondary analytical assessments, 2023–2025.

3. Sino-Russian cooperation in the Arctic: New features

By mid-2025, Sino-Russian cooperation in the Arctic has become a significant element of the two countries' strategic interaction. Both Russia and China regard joint projects as instruments for strengthening national interests, mitigating the consequences of sanctions pressure, and adapting to global instability. This dynamic reflects the reorientation of both states toward deepening bilateral cooperation under conditions of shrinking opportunities for engagement with Western countries.

Despite this shared orientation, the approaches of the two sides differ: Russia places emphasis on institutionalization and on using Chinese participation to support its own Arctic strategy, whereas China views cooperation as a tool for reinforcing logistical autonomy and energy security, while leaving room for caution and flexible adaptation. In Russia's interpretation, China is embedded in its national Arctic strategy, whereas in China's perspective, Russia is treated primarily as a resource within its global initiatives. At the same time, the institutional mechanisms of bilateral interaction continue to evolve and are being filled with new content.

Arctic issues have acquired a higher priority in the bilateral agenda since the start of the war in Ukraine. The Commission for the Preparation of Regular Meetings of the Heads of Government of Russia and China continues to operate (Russian Government, 2024), and annual Arctic consultations are held every September, receiving increasing attention (Zhilin, 2024). This reflects the gradual institutional consolidation of the Arctic in the strategic dialogue between the two states. The 2025 consultations, along with the second meeting of the Sino-Russian Subcommittee on the NSR, are expected to be more substantive and pragmatic. The first meeting was held at the end of 2024, headed on the Russian side by the Director General of Rosatom and on the Chinese side by the Minister of Transport, which demonstrates the high status of this working body (Rosatom, 2024). The format of participation indicates the consolidation of the NSR as an element of strategic interaction.

In Chinese assessments, Russia's Arctic activities and bilateral cooperation are interpreted as part of Beijing's strategy to strengthen autonomy and diversify logistical routes, shaped by intensifying geopolitical competition and global instability. In this perspective, the Arctic is regarded as a priority instrument for the long-term adaptation to the changing international environment.

The institutional basis of China's involvement is provided by the Development Group for the Russian Far East and Arctic. It oversees more than 3,500 investment projects, of which about 100 involve foreign participation, and 65 are implemented jointly with Chinese companies with a total value of around 1 trillion rubles, including projects in the Arctic zone. Chinese publications highlight the significance of such incentives as tax breaks, free customs zone regimes, and access to infrastructure, which reduce barriers for investors. According to China-Russia Media Platform (2025), these projects exemplify institutionalized interaction.

The amendments adopted in Russia in July 2025 to the 2014 Law on Territories of Advanced Development (TAD) (Russian Federation, 2014; 2025)—which provide for the launch of joint investment projects with foreign companies in the Far Eastern Federal District and the expansion of preferential regimes for foreign investors—are viewed in China as a step toward the institutionalization of international cooperation in the Arctic, aimed primarily at Chinese partners. The amendments will enter into force in 2026. Since the Far Eastern Federal District includes Arctic territories (Chukotka and northern Yakutia), the TAD regime may also be

applied in the Arctic. A separate provision on the branches of foreign banks within TADs opens channels for settlements and project financing, which are critically important for large-scale Arctic projects. The envisaged confidentiality of the Unified State Register of Legal Entities (EGRUL) regarding TAD residents reduces sanctions-related risks, while the mechanism of international treaties allows the establishment of special bilateral arrangements.

Particular attention is given to the initiative of establishing the largest Territory of Advanced Development (the so-called "Super TAD"), interpreted as an effort to consolidate existing preferential regimes in the Russian Far East and the Arctic. Chinese publications note that raising the minimum investment threshold to 10 million rubles will allow state support to be concentrated on large-scale initiatives, while stressing that opportunities for the participation of small and medium-sized Chinese businesses should be preserved (Russia Beyond, 2025).

In China, heightened attention is devoted to the updated Energy Strategy of the Russian Federation to 2050 (Russian Government, 2025a), considered an adaptive mechanism under sanctions and geoeconomic pressure. Analysts from CNPC's Information Center highlight the strategy's orientation toward energy autonomy, diversification of export routes, and the development of Arctic and Far Eastern infrastructure. According to their assessments, the strategy institutionalizes the country's "pivot to the East" and creates conditions for increasing Russia's presence in Asian energy markets. In the gas sector, a particular role is assigned to LNG projects: the operational Arctic LNG 2 and the planned Ob LNG and Murmansk LNG. Attention is also drawn to the risks associated with sanctions and technological constraints, yet the integration of gas infrastructure into a unified system, including the Sakhalin–Khabarovsk–Vladivostok route, is evaluated positively (China National Petroleum Corporation, 2025).

Cooperation on the NSR is regarded in China as a strategic priority. The work of the Sino-Russian coordinating body and the agreements reached on expanding cargo turnover are assessed positively (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the PRC, 2025). Efforts continue on the development of year-round container shipping within the joint venture between Rosatom and Hainan Yangpu New New Shipping, with St. Petersburg as the final port (Interfax, 2025). The development of related infrastructure—railway and river—is also under study (Global Times, 2025).

At the same time, in China there is growing concern over statements regarding the "realism" of U.S.–Russian cooperation in the Arctic. Such a shift weakens Beijing's position, as in recent years it has sought to consolidate its presence in the region, having declared itself a near-Arctic state in 2018 and linking the development of the Polar Silk Road to its partnership with Russia. Moscow's proposal to establish Arctic cooperation with Washington is perceived as a serious challenge: it could complicate the realization of China's ambitions in developing shipping routes, resource extraction, and infrastructure expansion. In Chinese commentary, it was even described as a "slap in the face" to Beijing, which had counted on special conditions for interaction with Russia in the Arctic (The Epoch Times, 2025a).

In 2025, the Russian side regards cooperation with China in the Arctic as an instrument for achieving strategic objectives in developing the Arctic zone and creating a sustainable geoeconomic model of the region. A central element is the linkage of the BRI with the projects of the Eurasian Economic Union. In documents of the Russian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, it is emphasized that such coordination makes it possible to bring the partnership "to a new level" and embed it in strategic interaction (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Russian Federation, 2025b).

The practical content of cooperation is being developed through multi-level platforms. For example, the forum "Sprouts: Russia and China — Mutually Beneficial Cooperation," held in Kazan in August 2025, brought together about 10,000 participants, including more than 200 Chinese companies. It addressed investment, transport corridors, tourism, and education, and new agreements were concluded between businesses and state institutions. The Consul General of China in Kazan, Xiang Bo, underscored the significance of the forum as a platform for local cooperation and highlighted the special role of Tatarstan in the development of Sino-Russian relations (Belt and Road portal, 2025; TASS, 2025f).

In the Arctic dimension, Russia's primary focus is on the development of the NSR as the main channel of access to Asian markets, conceived within the broader framework of the TATC. According to a recent assessment by Russia's ambassador to China, this route is becoming "the key gateway" to China (B-port, 2025). Within this logic, Russian projects such as Arctic LNG 2 are viewed as anchor points for Chinese investment and technology, while the task of ensuring year-round navigation is presented as a shared objective. Russia is fully aware of China's interest in creating logistical hubs on its territory. In this context, a project for a container hub involving Chinese and Indian companies is actively developing; it is integrated into the TATC, designed to diversify global trade routes by bypassing the Suez Canal (Lenta.ru, 2025). At the same time, preparations are underway in Arkhangelsk for the construction of a deep-water port, implemented by Rosatom and the logistics operator Eurosib in cooperation with Chinese partners (Pravda Severa, 2025). This project, which includes the introduction of automation and digitalization technologies, is intended to become a central element of the NSR's infrastructure base, contributing to the growth of cargo turnover, including import flows from China (Portnews, 2025).

Chinese participation is regarded as an important factor supporting the implementation of Russia's Energy Strategy to 2050 (Russian Government, 2025a). Within this framework, priority areas are defined as LNG projects (Ob LNG, Murmansk LNG, Arctic LNG 2) and the modernization of the gas transportation system. In this regard, the development of the NSR and the integration of the Far Eastern gas transportation infrastructure into a unified system (the Sakhalin–Khabarovsk–Vladivostok route) are seen as key elements reinforcing Russia's interconnection with China and, more broadly, with the Asia-Pacific region. Additional attention is drawn to the interest of Chinese partners in Arctic mineral resources—lithium, uranium, and rare earths—which is linked both to the global energy transition and to securing the sustainability of nuclear power generation.

At the same time, Russian analytical discussions acknowledge that Russia is compelled to take Chinese interests into account, seeking to maximize economic returns by leveraging its sovereign control over part of the Arctic (BUSINESS Online, 2025). In Russian discourse in 2025, cooperation with China is defined as a strategic direction in which logistics, energy, resources, and institutional mechanisms form a unified system. China is regarded as an investor and technological partner, but the framework of interaction remains under Russian control.

An analysis of Russian and Chinese positions shows that the Arctic is becoming an important zone where the interests of the two countries intersect, yet the logic of this intersection differs. For Russia, the key priority is to use Chinese investment, technology, and markets for the implementation of its long-term strategy for the development of the Arctic zone—ranging from the NSR, energy projects, and the mineral-resource base to broader institutional mechanisms. For China, cooperation with Russia serves both as a means of consolidating its position in the

Arctic as a near-Arctic state and as a mechanism for reducing the vulnerability of external supply chains and diversifying energy routes. At the same time, Beijing realistically assesses the risks—from sanctions to geopolitical challenges—which explains its caution in institutional consolidation and its orientation toward pragmatism. As a result, the Arctic functions not only as a platform for the convergence of Russian and Chinese interests but also as a space where the differences in their strategies set the boundaries and conditions of cooperation.

Table 2. Comparison of Russian and Chinese approaches to Arctic cooperation, 2025

Parameter	Russia	China
General orientation	Cooperation as part of the strategy for developing Russia's Arctic zone	Cooperation as an instrument of strategic autonomy and logistical diversification
Key projects	NSR, Trans-Arctic Transport Corridor (TATC), Arctic LNG 2, Arkhangelsk deep-water port, container hub	Participation in the NSR (Polar Silk Road), LNG projects (Arctic LNG 2, Ob LNG, Murmansk LNG), linkages with overland routes
Institutional basis	Sino-Russian Subcommission on the NSR, proposals for "Glavsevmorput 2.0" (modernized governance mechanism), updated Energy Strategy to 2050	Development Group for the Russian Far East and Arctic, TAD amendments, "Super TAD" mechanism, Polar Silk Road
Resource factor	Priority on LNG, gas infrastructure, and mineral resources (lithium, uranium, rare earths)	Interest in energy and mineral resources to support the global energy transition
Geopolitics	Cooperation with China as a way to overcome sanctions and strengthen Arctic leadership	Arctic as a space for consolidating near-Arctic status and reducing reliance on traditional routes
Constraints and challenges	Sanctions, technological constraints, investment needs	Risks of secondary sanctions, corporate caution, concerns about U.S. involvement in Arctic cooperation with Russia
Outlook	Institutionalization at the national level, integration of China into Russia's Arctic strategy to 2050	Flexible participation, pragmatic adaptation to changing conditions

Source: Compiled by the author based on official Russian and Chinese strategic documents, policy statements, and secondary analytical assessments, 2023–2025.

4. Maritime transport routes in the Arctic in the current strategic approaches of Russia and China

In the context of global warming and the gradual reduction of Arctic ice cover, the NSR is gaining increasing importance both as a potentially year-round transport corridor and as the main artery for Russia's key resource exploitation projects. For Russia, the NSR is closely linked to the formation of the TATC and to the pursuit of national objectives for the comprehensive advancement of the Arctic zone. For China, however, this route functions primarily as an instrument for diversifying global logistical connections and reducing dependence on vulnerable transit directions. Thus, in a rapidly changing geopolitical environment, the NSR is becoming strategically significant for both countries, yet their different motivations predetermine divergent interpretations and modes of utilization.

In Russia's Arctic policy of 2025, the NSR is redefined as the core of a new large-scale initiative—the TATC. The project envisions the integration of Arctic and domestic transport systems into a unified logistical network stretching from St. Petersburg to Vladivostok, with key hubs in Arkhangelsk and Murmansk. The TATC is conceived as a "seamless" corridor that combines maritime, railway, and road infrastructure.

The financial and economic model for the NSR/TATC is structured across two time horizons: up to 2030–2032, and with a longer perspective extending to 2040. Its main elements include the transition to year-round navigation based on a convoy system, fleet standardization, the expansion of the eastern sector of the NSR, and the establishment of predictable shipping schedules. Currently, 30 Arctic-class vessels are in operation, while an additional 67 are required; Russian production capacities remain limited, prompting the search for cooperation with foreign partners (NANGS, 2025).

At present, preparations are underway for a comprehensive plan for the Arctic in which the TATC will play a central role (Arctic Russia, 2025). The designated priorities include the modernization of port and transport infrastructure along the TATC, the creation of preferential conditions for shipping companies, and the provision of comprehensive security for the project.

A separate emphasis is placed on the institutionalization of TATC governance. Proposals include the establishment of a unified state operator combining the functions of strategic planning and interagency coordination, the transformation of TATC elements into implementable business projects, the attraction of investment, and the implementation of a long-term plan for Arctic policy. The conceptual model of the TATC envisions a route stretching from St. Petersburg through Arkhangelsk to Vladivostok (RIA Novosti, 2025a; TASS, 2025c).

At the St. Petersburg International Economic Forum 2025, the need was highlighted for a spatial-economic framework of Arctic zone development as a tool for the sustainable implementation of the TATC—integrating ports, inland waterways, railways, and road infrastructure into a single system (Prime, 2025). Rosatom has argued that state policy in the Russian Arctic—centered on the TATC concept—should be defined by a dedicated mechanism comparable in structure and importance to the national projects, while the overall planning horizon should extend to 2050 (Finmarket, 2025).

As a result, the contemporary understanding of the NSR in Russia reflects a shift from a stand-alone maritime route to the supporting backbone of the TATC, oriented toward transport and technological sovereignty, long-term comprehensive planning (to 2050), sustainable and mutually beneficial cooperation, and the institutionalization of a unified corridor with international participation and export orientation (Transport Rossii, 2025).

By contrast, China interprets the route along Russia's Arctic coast differently, embedding it in the framework of global logistics and linking it above all to the task of diversifying foreign trade.

The NSR is currently viewed in China not merely as an alternative maritime passage but as a key element of an emerging global transport system that underpins China's strategic autonomy. The central motivation behind this approach is the desire to reduce dependence on the Malacca Strait, which is surrounded by states hosting U.S. military forces and is perceived in Beijing as the most vulnerable link in China's external trade (Sohu News, 2025).

Amid intensifying geopolitical competition, China is actively seeking ways to diversify its transport channels, and the Arctic route through Russian waters appears especially attractive. It provides direct access to Europe, minimizes the number of transit states, and is protected by the Russian fleet—which reduces the likelihood of third-party interference, both military and legal. The Arctic also acquires added significance due to climate change, which creates the preconditions for year-round navigation. The NSR makes it possible to shorten the delivery time of Chinese cargoes to Europe by 10–15 days compared with routes through the Suez Canal or around Africa (Global Times, 2025). This is particularly important for high-value and time-sensitive goods—electronics, auto parts, and equipment—where speed and reliability of supply are paramount.

This vision of the NSR fits well into China's Belt and Road Initiative. The Arctic route is considered alongside other alternatives to the Malacca Strait—such as the China–Pakistan Economic Corridor leading to Gwadar Port or pipelines through Myanmar. In this context, the Arctic becomes not just a new direction but a "safety rope" capable of cushioning external logistical shocks and stabilizing export–import chains under conditions of international turbulence (Sohu News, 2025). Already in 2025, the NSR has been integrated into the logistics of Chinese manufacturers: the "sea + railway" model via Arkhangelsk and further along the Trans-Siberian Railway is actively used, enabling the creation of flexible and scalable supply routes (Global Times, 2025). In this regard, China has also shown interest in infrastructure and energy cooperation with Russia, including the joint development and production of equipment adapted to Arctic conditions—particularly technologies designed with environmental sensitivity.

Nevertheless, despite its strategic appeal, Chinese shipping and logistics companies remain cautious about the regular and large-scale use of the NSR (Xinde Marine News, 2025). The main reason for such restraint lies in a combination of geopolitical, operational, and environmental risks that hinder the institutionalization of the route.

The NSR runs almost entirely through Russian territorial waters, which makes it geopolitically vulnerable and dependent on Russia's political course and the current state of international relations. Intensifying sanctions pressure and limited access to global insurance and financial systems create serious barriers to the commercial expansion of the route. Even Chinese companies formally not subject to sanctions must take into account the risks of secondary

restrictions, as well as the challenges of operating with Russian ports and icebreaking infrastructure.

Despite its significant geographical advantages, the NSR remains a technically demanding route. Navigation requires the availability of specialized ice-class vessels, additional insurance, and well-trained crews. Moreover, as highlighted by recent disruptions in major maritime chokepoints—such as recurrent congestion in the Suez Canal, drought-related restrictions in the Panama Canal, and China’s own concerns over the vulnerability of the Malacca Strait (Seatrade Maritime News, 2025)—shipping companies are highly sensitive to geopolitical and operational risks. This reinforces the perception of the NSR as a route whose large-scale commercial utilization will remain cautious.

Finally, an important factor is the environmental agenda. Since 2019, leading international shipping corporations have signed the Arctic Shipping Corporate Pledge, which provides for a refusal to use Arctic routes in order to protect the environment. China, which actively promotes the international climate agenda and sustainable development, cannot ignore these trends: a significant increase in shipping is associated with environmental risks, including water pollution and the destruction of unique ecosystems.

Empirical data also corroborate the route’s limited commercial uptake: in 2024, cargo volumes totaled just 37.9 million tons (ERAI, 2025), roughly forty times lower than the Suez Canal’s 1.57 billion tons in 2023 (Wright, 2025). Chinese companies NewNew Shipping and Safetrans Line, which have close ties to Russia, have so far confined themselves to pilot voyages and have not signaled plans to scale up use of the NSR.

Taken together, Russian and Chinese perspectives reveal two diverging approaches to the NSR.

A comparative analysis of their strategies shows that behind the outward similarity of interest in the NSR lie essentially different views of the Arctic. For Russia, it is conceived as an internal space of national consolidation, where the maritime artery becomes the backbone of the TATC, linked not only to infrastructural integration but also to the development of the region’s vast natural resources. For China, by contrast, the Arctic remains an external direction, where the NSR is regarded as a safety channel of global trade, embedded in the Belt and Road Initiative and used selectively due to sanctions-related, technical, and environmental constraints. These two approaches complement each other, providing a basis for cooperation, but at the same time delineate the boundaries of interaction: Russia seeks institutionalization and control, while China prefers flexibility and cautious integration. In this sense, the NSR becomes not only a transport route but also an arena where Russia’s resource-oriented priorities intersect with China’s logistical interests.

In summary, the two approaches reflect distinct logics of engagement with the NSR. For Russia, the route is consolidated as a national project, institutionally formalized in the form of the TATC, aimed at ensuring transport and technological sovereignty and long-term planning for Arctic development. For China, it is treated as an element of global logistics diversification within the Belt and Road Initiative, while business caution persists due to sanctions, operational, and environmental risks. The main parameters of this comparison are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison of Russian and Chinese approaches to the Northern Sea Route

Parameter	Russia	China
Conceptualization	NSR as a national transport artery within the broader TATC	NSR as part of the Polar Silk Road, positioned as an international corridor
Strategic aim	Strengthening sovereignty, securing Asian market access, integrating Arctic into national development	Diversifying trade routes, reducing dependence on chokepoints (e.g., Malacca Strait), embedding Arctic routes into BRI
Institutional mechanisms	Rosatom as infrastructure operator; Sino-Russian Subcommission on the NSR; proposals for "Glavsevmorput 2.0"	Ministry of Transport (PRC), Development Group for the Russian Far East and Arctic, involvement of Chinese shipping companies (NewNew Shipping, Safetrans)
Infrastructure focus	Arkhangelsk deep-water port, container hub, LNG terminals, digitalization of the NSR	Port of Dalian as hub; linkage with Chinese Northeast provinces (Heilongjiang, Jilin, Liaoning); plans for "Land–Ice Silk Road" (Irtysh–Ob axis)
Economic role	Anchor for LNG exports and mineral development, supported by preferential regimes (TAD, "Super TAD")	Complementary to overland corridors, part of BRI logistics diversification
Constraints	Harsh climate, high costs of ice-class fleet, sanctions limiting technology and finance	Caution of companies due to sanctions, environmental concerns, uncertainty of Russia's dialogue with the U.S.
Outlook	Consolidation of the NSR within national strategy, pursuit of year-round navigation, gradual inclusion of Asian partners	Incremental involvement, pilot voyages, selective investments, integration with broader BRI projects

Source: Compiled by the author based on official Russian and Chinese strategic documents, policy statements, and secondary analytical assessments, 2023–2025.

5. Conclusions

The analysis conducted shows that by 2025 Sino-Russian cooperation in the Arctic had acquired a more systemic and institutionalized character, yet its foundation remains primarily pragmatic rather than one of deep strategic convergence. Russia seeks to consolidate its priorities through the implementation of the Trans-Arctic Transport Corridor (TATC) concept, the development of northern territories, and the strengthening of naval presence, as well as by using the Arctic theme in international forums to reaffirm its status as a leading Arctic state.

China, by contrast, integrates the Arctic dimension into the broader framework of its Eurasian strategy, linking it with the development of Russia's Far East and the Belt and Road Initiative. For Beijing, the Arctic is becoming part of a comprehensive approach that combines transport routes, energy, scientific and humanitarian cooperation, while retaining an emphasis on flexibility and caution. Thus, Russia's strategy focuses on the protection and institutionalization of its own interests, whereas China's strategy centers on diversification and the pursuit of greater logistical autonomy.

The institutional mechanisms of bilateral interaction—from regular consultations to the Subcommission on the NSR—have demonstrated their capacity to compensate for limited political trust and to create working formats that ensure steady development of cooperation. However, these mechanisms do not eliminate contradictions; they merely relegate them to the margins of the agenda.

The identified differences in strategic orientations indicate that the convergence of Russia and China in the Arctic is primarily tactical. Moscow relies on China as a partner under sanctions pressure and in the face of the need for large-scale investment, while Beijing views cooperation as an instrument for diversifying supplies and strengthening energy security, avoiding excessive dependence on Russia.

The forecast for the coming years is that the institutionalization of cooperation will continue to deepen, especially in transport and energy, as well as in scientific and technological collaboration. At the same time, the enduring divergence of strategic priorities will limit the possibility of forming a unified long-term model. Cooperation will most likely remain pragmatic, developing in those areas where short-term interests converge. In the context of global confrontation with the United States, Arctic cooperation will retain for China an instrumental character and for Russia the role of a compensatory mechanism, but its sustainability will depend on the ability of both sides to align their priorities and adapt to a changing international environment.

At the same time, the resilience of cooperation will increasingly depend on the capacity of both states to integrate environmental and climate considerations into their strategic projects, as well as on China's reliance on soft-power instruments—scientific diplomacy, cultural exchange, and informational outreach—to reinforce its legitimacy as a near-Arctic state. Moreover, Russia's efforts to engage partners from the Global South suggest that the trajectory of Sino-Russian cooperation may ultimately be embedded in a broader multipolar framework, where Russia's institutionalization and China's flexibility coexist as complementary rather than opposing logics.

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